

Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Rhodium with 1-Phenyl-3-Thiobenzoyl Thiocarbamide

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A procedure for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of rhodium with 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide is described. Effects due to acid concentration, salting out agents, reagent concentration, stannous chloride concentration, extraction solvents and diverse ions were evaluated. Beer's law was obeyed between 0 to 5 ppm and the molar absorptivity at 325 nm was 3.1×10^4 .

It has been found that the platinum group elements show great reactivity with thio-organic compounds. A number of methods, using sulphur containing organic compounds as gravimetric and extracting reagents for rhodium, have been described¹⁻⁷. Some recently introduced reagents for rhodium are monobenzoylthiourea⁸, N,N-diphenylthiourea⁹, phthalimide dithiosemicarbazone¹⁰ and *o*-methylpicolinaldehyde thiosemicarbazone¹¹.

In the present communication, the use of a new thioreagent, 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide (PTT) for the extraction photometric determination of rhodium is described. Extraction studies for platinum with PTT have been described earlier^{1,2}. Unlike most other thio reagents, rhodium reacts with PTT at room temperature (28°) and is quantitatively extracted into ethylacetate. Complexation occurs in 2 M HCl medium in the presence of stannous chloride.

Experimental

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckman Model DU 2 Spectrophotometer using optically matched 10 mm quartz cells.

Reagents: Standard rhodium solution. A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (JMC) in 500 ml of 1 M hydrochloric acid and was standardized by the usual method¹³. Test solutions were prepared by suitably diluting a portion of the stock solution with 1 M hydrochloric acid.

Ethyl acetate: British Drug House (AR) grade.

1-Phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide (PTT): Prepared and crystallized as previously described^{13,14}.

Stannous chloride: A 3% solution in 3 M HCl was used.

Procedure: An aliquot of the test solution (containing 5-50 μg of rhodium) is transferred to a 125 ml separatory funnel and 18 ml 2 M HCl, 1 ml SnCl_2 solution and 5 ml 3×10^{-4} M PTT solution

in acetone are added in succession. 10 ml of ethyl acetate is added and the mixture shaken vigorously for 1 min. The organic layer is collected in a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to the mark, and allowed to stand 1.5 hr. The absorbance at 325 nm is then measured against a reagent blank. The amount of rhodium is calculated from a previously prepared calibration graph.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectrum of the Rh(III) complex in ethyl acetate shows an absorbance maximum at 325 nm (Fig. 1A). The reagent blank shows a continuous decrease in

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra
(A) Absorption spectra of the complex against reagent blank Rh(III)=15 μg , 1 ml 3% SnCl_2 , 5 ml PTT of 3×10^{-4} M in acetone.
(B) Absorption spectra of the reagent blank against solvent.

absorption over the region of maximum absorbance of the Rh complex (Fig. 1B). The molar absorptivity of the Rh complex in ethyl acetate at 325 nm was 3.1×10^4 and the Sandell sensitivity was $0.0033 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Effect of acidity: Quantitative extraction occurs in the acid range of 2-4 M. Extraction is incomplete above and below these concentrations.

Period of equilibration and stability : A 30 sec shaking period is found to be sufficient for complete extraction. However, in the present studies shaking was done for 1 min. Also one extraction with 10 ml or two extractions with 5 ml each of ethyl acetate do not show any difference in absorbance. The colour of the organic layer attains full intensity after 1.5 hr and then remains unchanged for 20 hr. After that period the absorbance decreases.

Conformity to Beer's law : The absorbances of solutions containing increasing amounts of rhodium were measured against a reagent blank at 325 nm. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range of 0 to 5 ppm. The optimum working range as obtained from a Ringbom plot was 0.631 to 1.995 ppm (Fig. 2 A and B).

Fig. 2. (A) Calibration curve.

Fig. 2. (B) Ringbom plot.

Effect of salting out agents : The addition of chloride and nitrate of alkali metals and alkaline earths, maintained in a 0.5 to 2 M concentration range, did not enhance the extraction.

Effect of reagent concentration : To 20 ml of 2 M HCl acid solution containing 15 µg of rhodium and stannous chloride, varying concentration of

PTT in acetone were added. The results showed that 5 ml of 3.0×10^{-4} M PTT was suitable for extraction.

Effect of stannous chloride concentration : Rhodium alone does not react with PTT but does so only in presence of stannous chloride. Studies on the effect of the concentration of stannous chloride showed that addition of 1 ml of 3% through 10% solution did not change the absorbance.

Effect of other acids : Besides hydrochloric acid, hydrobromic, perchloric and sulphuric acids were tried but none of them was found to be suitable. In hydrobromic acid the extraction was almost negligible. Ethyl acetate was found to be miscible with perchloric acid. In sulphuric acid the extraction was 63.3%.

Effect of other solvents : Extractions were carried out using various solvents. The results showed that extraction into chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene and ethyl acetate was 36.6, 20, 40, 50 and 100% respectively. A scum was observed at the interphase when using all other solvents except ethyl acetate.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of several anions and cations on the extraction behaviour of rhodium was studied. An error of $\pm 1.5\%$ in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. The studies made with 15 µg of rhodium led to the following observations. Cations which are generally associated with rhodium and minerals and showing tolerance limit more than 15 µg are Pt^{4+} , Ir^{3+} and Pd^{2+} . Ions such as S^{2-} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Te^{3+} show tolerance limit of the order of 450 µg. Other common anions and cations show a high tolerance limit of more than 1000 µg. The interference caused by osmium and copper may be removed by selectively extracting them with tetramethyl-thiuram disulphide (TMTD) prior to the analysis of rhodium. Copper¹⁵ forms an extractable complex with TMTD at pH 3.5. Osmium¹⁶ may also be selectively extracted with TMTD into toluene in 7 M HCl.

Precision and accuracy. A number of measurements (10 or more) were taken at a given concentration (usually 3 different ones). In the measurement of 1.0-2.0 ppm of Rh standard deviation was found to be 0.056 to 0.070 ppm and the percentage relative error was from 0.033 to 0.20%.

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